

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TERMS RELATED TO TRADITION IN ENGLISH, UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

Tolibaeva Ayjamal Tolibay qizi

**2nd year master student of the specialty “Linguistics (English language), Karakalpak
State University**

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Abstract. A study of traditional terms in typology can give important insights into the linguistic and cultural development of a specific language or language family. The use of traditional terms can provide insight into the social and historical context in which a language developed because they frequently reflect the values, beliefs, and customs of a community. In order to compare terms related to tradition in English, Uzbek, and Karakalpak, the article does so.

Keywords: linguistics, culture, tradition, typology, English, Uzbek, Karakalpak, literature, example.

We use traditional terms to acknowledge and respect the cultural heritage and practices of different communities. These terms help us understand and appreciate the diversity of human experience and promote cultural awareness and sensitivity. Additionally, traditional practices and knowledge can offer valuable insights and solutions to contemporary problems, particularly in areas such as healthcare and environmental sustainability [3, 18-28]. By using traditional terms, we can also help preserve and protect these cultural practices for future generations. Therefore, the article presents the comparison of terms related to tradition in English, Uzbek and Karakalpak languages.

The terms related to tradition can be classified as follows:

1. Heritage, Ancestry, Oral history, Indigenous knowledge, Intangible cultural heritage, Sacred knowledge - These terms refer to the historical and cultural legacy passed down from previous generations.
2. Custom, Culture, Beliefs, Values, Folklore, Rituals, Traditional practices, Local wisdom - These terms refer to the social norms, customs, and practices that are specific to a particular community or group of people. They are often shaped by cultural beliefs and values.
3. Traditional medicine - This term refers to the medicinal practices and remedies that have been used for generations by a particular community or group of people. It is often based on local knowledge and resources.

The following terms are widely known terms related to tradition in English, Uzbek and Karakalpak languages:

English	Uzbek	Karakalpak
1. Tradition	1. Odat	Úrp-ádet
2. Custom	2. Adat	Ádebiyat
3. Heritage	3. Tarix	Folklor
4. Culture	4. Madaniyat	Miyras
5. Folklore	5. Folklor	Qádriyat
6. Ritual	6. Adabiyot	Mádeniyat
7. Ancestry	7. O'yin	Húrmet
8. Convention	8. Ota-onalar merosi	Ata-babalar

9. Legacy 10. Inheritance	9. Turmush tarzi 10. Farzand tarbiyasi	Tárbiya Máresim
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In English, tradition refers to a long-established custom or belief that has been passed down from generation to generation. Custom and heritage also refer to practices and beliefs that have been passed down through generations. Culture encompasses the customs, arts, beliefs, and social institutions of a particular group of people. Folklore refers to the traditional stories, beliefs, and customs of a culture or community.

Ritual refers to a set of actions or words performed in a specific way as part of a religious or cultural ceremony. Ancestry refers to one's family or lineage, while convention refers to a widely accepted practice or behavior.

Legacy and inheritance both refer to something that is passed down from one generation to the next, but legacy often refers to something intangible like values or beliefs, while inheritance refers to physical possessions or property.

In Uzbek, odat and adat and in Karakalpak úrp-ádet refer to customs and traditions that have been passed down through generations. Tarix and qádriyat refers specifically to history, while madaniyat and mádeniyat encompass all aspects of culture and civilization [1, 796-800].

Folklor and adabiyot and in Karakalpak Folklor and ádebiyat refer to traditional stories, beliefs, and literature of a culture or community. O'yin refers to games or play, while otonalar merosi and ata-babalar miyrasi refer to family gatherings or celebrations [4].

Turmush tarzi refers to the way of life or customs of a family or household, while farzand tarbiyasi and tárbiya refer to the upbringing and education of children.

As can be seen the traditional terms in the compared languages are similar in the usage so that it can be said that there is a close relationship between these languages in the case of traditional terms.

- Conclusion. Taking all into account it can be concluded that traditional terms in English, Karakalpak, and Uzbek should be compared in order to better understand the cultural similarities and differences. Understanding the significance of each culture's values, beliefs, and traditions, as well as how they have been passed down through the generations, is helpful. We can learn more about the historical and cultural factors that have shaped each culture by contrasting these terms. This may result in a greater understanding and respect for various cultures and traditions.

References:

1. Hilola Namitdinovna Rashidova (2020). THE CONCEPT OF TERM AND TERMINOLOGY IN LINGUISTICS. Academic research in educational sciences, (3), 796-800.
2. Абдуллаева А. Лексика сферы международных отношений (на материале русского и узбекского языков). Автореф. дисс. канд. филол. наук. - Ташкент, 2003.
3. Гринев-Гриневич С.В., Сорокина Э.А. Перспективные направления развития терминологических исследований // Вестник МГОУ. Серия: Лингвистика. 2018. №5. - С. 18-28
4. Д.С. Насыров, М.К. Айымбетов. «Jigirmalanshi' a'sir Qaraqalpaq terminologiyasi», Обложка Нукус «Илим» 2013 год.
5. Миртожиев М. Ўзбек тили семасиологияси-Тошкент: Мумтоз сўз, 2010.